

STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEK

ANIMATION DATE

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***Abstract.** This article is related to tradition and innovation in Uzbek animated films and is important for the assessment of the role of animation in the process of civilization, the stages of development of Uzbek animation, scientific and creative research, and its scientific analysis. Many problems can be overcome today by analyzing the process of creating animated films.*

***Keywords.** Animation, cinema, computer graphics, cinematography, multimedia.*

The art of cinema is a means of enriching the world of thinking through the development of spirituality, artistic, aesthetic, and emotional impact. The period from independence to the present day is the period of revival and development of Uzbek animation[1]. From this period, the art of Uzbek animation began, which, having reached creative and stylistic diversity, demonstrated its characteristic artistic features.

Today, computer graphics are widely used in a variety of fields. It is widely used in advertising, music videos, TV series, science, and technology, when creating various physiologically complex phenomena, in medicine. Computer graphics have a special place in cinematography and are very effective in creating backgrounds, characters, digital makeup, and special effects.

Creating computer graphics in films is a complex process that requires a lot of work from hundreds of masters of their craft. The writer, director, and 3D art team

work on the modeling, texturing, animation, rigging, and rendering of characters and objects in the virtual universe[2].

Feature films with animated elements have their laws and aesthetic features. Here, combinations of "live" images and "inanimate" characters are in harmony with objects that do not exist in the real world. Today, the use of such effects allows you to expand the expressiveness of the frame due to the endless possibilities of computer animation. In the art of cinema, computer animation is becoming a new form of artistic consciousness, effectively depicting real and fictional reality.

Cinematography plays an important role in shaping the spiritual world and the aesthetic taste of a person. Animated films with a high degree of impact, rich in bright characters, and unique plots, occupy a worthy place in the upbringing of a harmoniously developed generation. Today, the attention paid to the art of cinema in our country, including the demand for the creation of animated films, has changed for the better.

Gradually, national cartoons began to replace foreign cartoons broadcast on television. The growing integration of our country into the world economy, the launch of new industries, and the modernization of production have increased the need for qualified specialists with advanced knowledge and skills in various fields. Given the current needs of the labor market, the training of highly qualified specialists is considered a priority. Educational work is constantly being improved, teaching standards meet international standards and modern requirements. New specializations are created following socio-economic development, harmonizing theory, practice, and production.

Based on the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 26, 2016 "On admission to higher educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the 2016-2017 academic year", 18 areas of study were opened in higher educational institutions[3]. According to the specified resolution, the Uzbek State Institute of Arts and Culture began to accept students in a new specialty. Now

the program of creative examinations for applicants for undergraduate studies in the specialty "Animation and multimedia design in art", the acceptance of documents and entrance examinations are conducted following the "Rules for admission to educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan".

Animation and multimedia design in art is an educational field in the field of art and culture, which includes a set of modern technical devices and devices, equipment and effective means of modern special and complex computer technologies, ways of working with animated graphics programs in painting, design, directing, and cinematography[4]. Applicants who wish to become an animation director must meet the following requirements:

- have an idea about the types of animation and animators;
- have an understanding of the role of the arts in screen art, animated films, and television films and shows;
- think logically and creatively;
- have an idea about literature, fine arts, and music;
- knowledge of ethics, rules of conduct, the presence of aesthetic taste and worldview;
- The director must have analytical skills.

Specialists who have been trained in the field of animation and multimedia design in the art will certainly contribute to the development of our country and the development of domestic cinema.

Based on the foregoing, today the process of training young animators, to create cartoons in Uzbek cinema is taking place and will continue, therefore, it is impossible to assess the situation as unambiguously positive because at present we have very few professional animators and authors. This system is analyzed and evaluated by each creator in his way. On the other hand, most of our animated film viewers are young people. Taking into account this point of view, the following measures should be taken at the initial stage:

- development of domestic cinema, including animation, following modern requirements;

- improving the quality of products using modern technologies;
- holding competitions, and festivals;
- efficient organization of cartoons distribution;
- study the experience of successful film studios in the field of animation;
- organization of refresher courses.

With the gradual solution of the above problems, the audience will also form a unique taste and desire, and as a result, domestic animated films will receive greater respect and love not only in our country but also in the world of animation.

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